

A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE STARTS FROM THE FAMILY

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Abstract. *In today's world of intensive development of the economy and social complex of activities, great importance and special attention is paid to issues of health and spiritual and moral education of the younger generation. The main link in this work is the family, because it is here that a person is formed as an individual, and the family is the keeper of centuries-old national traditions and the experience of folk pedagogy. Human health is directly formed in the family and affects all aspects of society as a whole. The formation of a healthy family lifestyle will lead to an improvement in the quality of life of the population, strengthening the health of the population through the protection of motherhood and childhood, reducing child and maternal mortality, which is achieved through family planning.*

Keywords: *formation, healthy lifestyle, family, improvement, quality, life, population, strengthening, health.*

For the successful development of a family, it is necessary, first of all, to maintain the health of the mother, ensure a healthy interval between births, and ultimately, the birth of a healthy child. For the full and effective growth of children's development in the first year of life, the most acceptable nutrition is breastfeeding. Feeding children with mother's milk creates psycho-emotional closeness between mother and child and provides a favorable environment for the normal physical and psychological development of the child. The act of breastfeeding helps develop the child's attachment to the mother. This regular physical contact leads to an improvement in the child's general condition, his health, and subsequently his individual adaptability to life. The main task of society and family is the comprehensive education of a healthy generation and preparing it for life in society. One of the most important tasks in the development of the younger generation is the rational organization of physical culture and sports, the activation of the motor regime starting from early childhood throughout life. In order for children to engage in physical education from an early age, we adults must become an example for them in our family [1.5]

The family is the most basic unit when raising a child, because the child spends a significant part of his life here. A child acquires his very first social skills in the family. The upbringing, formation of a healthy lifestyle of a child, organization, and planning of his life begins, first of all, with the education of adults themselves and with the organization of the life of the family as a whole, which is achieved by creating highly moral intra-family relationships that ensure a healthy environment in the family. The effectiveness of pedagogical and social influences depends on a healthy family environment, and it should be noted that young children are more susceptible to educational influences and skills, especially if the child grows up in an atmosphere of friendship, trust and mutual relationships. They observe the relationships of adults, their emotional reactions and feeling, studying for themselves all the diversity of manifestations of feelings of loved ones, the child acquires moral and educational skills and experiences. By nature, a child is more active, mobile and inquisitive, he easily perceives everything he hears and sees around him, all this is passed on to him from adults. It is also important that what kind of psycho-emotional impressions

he receives, positive or negative: love, care, tenderness, goodwill, respect for others or irritability, grumpiness, envy, gloomy faces, pettiness and others. A child needs a serious attitude and genuine attention from adults. Children appreciate this and are drawn to those who understand and support their interests and plans. Love for a child should not be in words, but in the actions and actions of an adult [2]. The spiritual and moral education of children in the family is the main foundation of the future. Therefore, from an early age, children need to form an understanding of national traditions, customs and cultural behavior. The spiritual development of a child mainly depends on a calm and friendly relationship in the family. A child raised in a healthy family becomes a spiritually mature, healthy and independent-minded person. The basis of spiritual and moral education in children is the priority of love and empathy in the family. The spiritual and moral education of a child can be ensured in a friendly atmosphere in the family, its duration, the degree of awareness of the personal “I” of human qualities, the general development of one’s horizons and one’s independent thinking. Here, an important role in the spiritual and moral education of a child is played by mutual respect for the performance of their duties by family members, the relationship of family members among themselves, relatives, neighbors and empathy for loved ones. If we as adults are committed to maintaining a spiritual connection with our children, we must recognize the need to work on stopping treating our little ones with disrespect. It is respect for the child that will allow us to raise a new generation of leaders who will lead our country forward in the future, bring new victories and achievements, and build a humane, fair, prosperous society.

The content of education, work carried out in the family with children develops a sense of dignity for their family, country, people, language, religion, and the place where they were born, grew up and developed. Raising and teaching children in the family as a human person, developing a sense of dignity, friendship, hospitality, love of work, the pursuit of knowledge and mastering a profession, contributes to the development of family and patriotic feelings, a sense of justice and rules of behavior in everyday life and in society [3].

The formation of a child’s personality is influenced not only by the family but also by the adult environment, the public in preschool and school institutions, on the street and in places of public entertainment. The most important thing here is that the child, receiving positive life skills from those around him, learns the ABCs of feelings and measures. It is important that others respect the child as an individual. At the same time, it is necessary to show delicacy and tact when communicating with children. Be able to talk to him and listen to them, always show support, and when a child’s disobedience or inattention causes irritation, you need to be able to choose methods and skills to influence the child, be able to understand him and the motives of his actions, stand in his place, decide what to do with him in fairness[4,5]. The most important thing when choosing methods of influence is to rely on all the best that the child has. When raising a child, one cannot fail to take into account that in each age period he acquires important and serious human qualities and life skills. Children look closely at adults, they have such an extraordinary ability to recognize the mood of their elders and become infected by them, they sensitively perceive how adults treat them. Are they ready to give in or demand leniency towards them, are they adamant, irritated or complacent? Young children have a greater tendency to imitate. The desire of children to imitate in most cases can help in education, especially if the child around him sees positive examples of the behavior of adults and his elders. A famous Polish teacher wrote: “The child knows those around him, their moods, their habits, their weaknesses, he knows them and uses them skillfully”.

He guesses the location, senses hypocrisy, grasps everything he sees and hears on the fly. The same feature of children often becomes the cause of negative manifestations, since a preschool child does not yet have a strong idea of what is good and what is bad. At the same time, according to his understanding, he is absolutely sure that everything that people older than him do is good. In various life situations, parents and other people around them must take into account the child's self-esteem, see him as a developing personality, and strive for mutual understanding based on respect and trust. Raising a child is a great art, since the process of education itself is a continuous work of the soul, mind, and parents and the public.

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